

UnWeaving the knots of GraphRAG – turns out VectorRAG is almost enough

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Abstract

One of the key problems in Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) systems is that chunk-based retrieval pipelines represent the source chunks as atomic objects, mixing the information contained within such a chunk into a single vector. These vector representations are then fundamentally treated as isolated, independent and self-sufficient, with no attempt to represent possible relations between them. Such an approach has no dedicated mechanisms for handling multi-hop questions.

Graph-based RAG systems aimed to ameliorate this problem by modeling information as knowledge-graphs, with entities represented by nodes being connected by robust relations, and forming hierarchical communities. This approach however suffers from its own issues with some of them being: orders of magnitude increased componential complexity in order to create graph-based indices, and reliance on heuristics for performing retrieval.

We propose UnWeaver, a novel RAG framework simplifying the idea of GraphRAG. UnWeaver disentangles the contents of the documents into entities which can occur across multiple chunks using an LLM. In the retrieval process entities are used as an intermediate way of recovering original text chunks hence preserving fidelity to the source material. We argue that entity-based decomposition yields a more distilled representation of original information, and additionally serves to reduce noise in the indexing, and generation process.¹

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¹Code is available at Github

1 Introduction

In this paper, we propose **UnWeaver**, a novel RAG framework that achieves better than graph-like retrieval precision without explicitly building a graph. The core idea is to provide to an LLM a query-relevant context based on vector similarity of an incoming query to the embeddings formed from the concatenated descriptions of equivalent entities (or, ideas) extracted from each document chunk. Based on that similarity of the query and the distilled entity-related content, distributed over all text chunks, query-relevant chunks are easily identified with a simple index (linear mapping). Then, the retriever produces relevant context from those chunks for LLM to perform well-grounded reasoning and accurate question answering.

The core novelty here is the concatenation of chunk-based (local) descriptions of equivalent entities extracted from each chunk separately. When transformed into embeddings, these aggregated entity descriptions filter out what is irrelevant while amplifying pertinent information in relevant chunks. The results of experimental studies support that claim by showing how facts and evidence in the produced context guide LLM towards good answers and support simple reasoning.

Related work: VectorRAG vs GraphRAG

Large language models (LLMs) augmented with retrieval have become a cornerstone for knowledge-intensive tasks, from question answering to fact-checking. In a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) framework, LLM is supplied with relevant external documents (or document fragments) as context, which helps ground its output in factual information.

This approach has been shown to significantly reduce open-domain hallucinations by allowing the model to draw on up-to-date or domain-specific knowledge instead of relying solely on parametric memory [16]. The original RAG system by Lewis et al. [14] demonstrated improved accuracy on knowledge-intensive NLP tasks by retrieving supporting passages.

The effectiveness of a RAG-based system hinges on the quality of retrieval. Irrelevant or poorly chosen context can inject false or unrelated facts, increasing probability of factual errors or flawed reasoning in responses generated by LLM.

One of key limitations of standard RAG pipelines is their reliance on coarse-grained text chunks. Documents are typically broken into fixed-length chunks that form the units of retrieval. While this helps the retrieved (hopefully) query-related context fit within LLM input limits, in practice these retrieved parts of available text may still contain superfluous or unrelated information. Consequently, RAG may amplify factual inaccuracies and hallucinations in generated responses, contrary to expectations [3]. Without external verification, LLMs generating response based on such a noisy context may follow off-topic details and incorporate them into their answers. Indeed, recent analyses confirm that filtering context yields noticeably more correct and concise answers [8].²

A promising way to address that problem is to incorporate structured knowledge graph (KG) into the RAG pipeline (see the survey [7]). The motivation for graph-based RAG (GraphRAG for short) is that a knowledge graph can represent information at a finer granularity. Knowledge graph essentially *unweaves* the source text into a graph of connected entities (e.g., people, places, concepts), with labeled edges representing discovered relationships (their strength, nature or description). Such graph-structured data can make it easier to reason over relevant facts without interference from unrelated context. In principle, the structured nature of a KG promises deeper and more

²In fact, as demonstrated by Karpowicz [12], since there is no way to eliminate LLM hallucinations, we can only manage the related tradeoffs. Designing RAG systems is one of the most reasonable ways to do that, provided we have a good way of retrieving relevant knowledge (in a way aligned with our preferences).

contextual retrieval than flat text similarity search.

Despite their well-known advantages, GraphRAG solutions come with significant practical challenges. Constructing and maintaining a graph index of a large text corpus is a non-trivial endeavor. Unlike vector index in VectorRAG systems built directly on text embeddings, a graph index requires multiple complex steps. These include, e.g., running named entity recognition, extracting relational triples or entity links, and possibly performing clustering or ontology alignment to organize the graph. This added componential complexity means high development and computation costs. For instance, the MSGraphRAG pipeline [4] involves building an entire knowledge graph from the corpus, then performing hierarchical community detection on the graph and generating summaries for each cluster—an elaborate process with many moving parts.

Furthermore, graph retrieval itself is less straightforward than vector similarity search. One cannot simply embed a query and do k -NN search over nodes. Instead, tailored algorithms or heuristics are needed to traverse or query the graph structure. Prior work has explored techniques like translating natural language questions into structured graph queries (in SPARQL or Cypher), performing multi-hop subgraph searches. But these often require dedicated graph database and careful hand-tuning of query logic. As a result, GraphRAG typically demands orders of magnitude more engineering effort and can suffer from scalability issues when dealing with millions of nodes or edges.

All that raises an intriguing question. Is it possible to obtain the benefits of graph-based retrieval—improved relevance and reduced noise—without the heavy machinery of full-scale knowledge graphs?

Contributions The approach we propose in this paper leverages entity-centric retrieval inspired by knowledge graphs, yet it maintains the simplicity and speed of a standard vector-based pipelines (operating on refined text embeddings). That suggests there is really no need for complex and costly graph traversal or maintaining separate graph databases when documents contain separable ideas that can be named and described without much ambiguity.

Figure 1: Architecture of UnWeaver

Our experimental results show that UnWeaver yields higher answer accuracy and faithfulness compared to conventional chunk retrieval baselines, demonstrating a clear reduction in hallucinated or off-target details. Moreover, this is achieved with negligible additional latency, since the entity-indexing step is done offline and query-time retrieval remains a fast embedding lookup.

UnWeaver remains firmly rooted in a standard vector-RAG framework, but enriches each indexed chunk with distilled semantic signals instead of building an explicit graph. Each stored vector therefore implicitly carries a lightweight summary of its content (e.g., key entities). At query time, these enriched embeddings bias the search toward passages that share the same salient entities, effectively filtering out irrelevant context. As a result, UnWeaver’s retrieved context is far more coherent: it can mitigate data noise and reinforce logical coherence in its results, all while requiring no graph operations and preserving the efficiency of standard ANN search. In short, UnWeaver attains the benefits of GraphRAG-style structured retrieval (reduced noise, higher precision, etc.) within a pipeline that is close to pure vector-RAG.

Conceptually, UnWeaver redefines the vector index

as an intelligent knowledge store, rather than a flat list of embeddings. Each stored vector is augmented with multi-level signals: alongside the raw text embedding we include a concise abstraction of the chunk’s key entities (a kind of mini-graph summary). This hybrid encoding lets the retriever match on deeper features: nearest neighbors are found not just by lexical similarity, but by shared conceptual relations – effectively capturing the intra- and inter-document connectivity that arises from explicit entity-relation structure. Crucially, these semantic gains come at no cost in scalability: the same ANN infrastructure is used, with only a lightweight preprocessing step to extract entity/relation features. In summary, UnWeaver can be thought of as not merely a compromise between GraphRAG and VectorRAG, but a principled extension of the VectorRAG paradigm that amplifies salient knowledge signals within a simple vector-retrieval framework. Furthermore, the addition of entity-based index to VectorRAG framework allows for better explainability of results since entities/ideas are inherently more explainable than raw passages of text that are returned indiscriminately by typical VectorRAG.

So, we make the following contributions in this

paper.

UnWeaver Framework: We introduce UnWeaver, a novel RAG architecture that eradicates non-essential information from candidate retrieval chunks and focuses on salient, query-relevant content. To our knowledge, this is one of the first frameworks to successfully combine entity-centric indexing with traditional vector retrieval for RAG. This architecture can be seen on Figure 1.

Entity-Based Indexing Pipeline: We develop an effective pipeline for building an entity-based index from unstructured text. This pipeline captures the core factual elements of documents (akin to a knowledge graph) without requiring full graph construction, thereby combining the precision and explainability of graph-based retrieval with the simplicity of standard dense retrieval.

Improved Retrieval Fidelity: Through comprehensive experiments on knowledge-intensive QA benchmarks, we demonstrate that UnWeaver significantly reduces retrieval noise and improves answer fidelity compared to standard GraphRAG approaches. It outperforms baseline chunk retrieval methods in grounding LLM outputs to the correct sources, which in turn mitigates hallucinations and increases factual accuracy of the generated responses.

Practical Insights for RAG: We analyze the trade-offs between graph-augmented and purely text-based RAG, and discuss why UnWeaver’s strategy can achieve the best of both worlds. Our findings suggest that many benefits of GraphRAG can be attained with far less complexity. This has important implications for designing the next generation of efficient and trustworthy RAG systems, indicating that graphs are not what you need if your goal is high-quality retrieval augmentation without undue overhead.

2 Mathematics of UnWeaver

We begin with an informal description of the algorithm. The unstructured data are passed into a (possibly multimodal) generative language model after segmentation into chunks. The language model produces a structured output listing entities mentioned within the chunk along with their descriptions. An

LLM outputs across the entire document base are then aggregated, to recognize recurring entities, while retaining links to their original sources (chunks). Each entity is assigned a vector by the embedder, based on the textual representation of its features, and these are inserted into the vector store. During retrieval, the query is compared to the entity vector store, to recover the most relevant entities. The links to original document sources are then recovered and aggregated (e.g. by means of voting), to produce the most relevant document chunks. The retrieved document chunks are passed into the generator LLM, to provide the final answer.

Formalized Characterization Assume we are given a text T (or a set of texts, documents, etc.) that will serve as the data for our RAG task. Let $C_T = (c_1, \dots, c_n)$ be the list of chunks that the aforementioned text T is divided into by some tokenizer – i.e., C_T is simply the segmented version of our text T . That is the first (trivial) step of our framework.

In the second step, an LLM generates names of entities together with their descriptions, from the chunks, the result of which is n lists L_1, \dots, L_n of pairs in the following form – for each $i \leq n$: $L_i = (e_1, \dots, e_{k_i})$, where for each $j \leq k_n$ the entity e_j has the form $e_j = (n_j^i, d_j^i)$, where n_j^i is a name of the entity, and d_j^i is the description of the entity, generated by the LLM from the chunk c_i (and, possibly, its internal parameters). We then glue the entities into equivalence classes of the relation of syntactic equivalence. In other words, we identify the entities $e_a = (n_a, d_a)$ and $e_b = (n_b, d_b)$, if the corresponding names n_a and n_b are syntactically equivalent.

Next, given an entity e_a , and its equivalence class $[e_a]_{\approx_{name}} = \{e_{a_1}, \dots, e_{a_k}\}$,³ we define its representative \tilde{e}_a as the following pair: $\tilde{e}_a := (n_a, \tilde{d}_a)$, where $\tilde{d}_a = d_{a_1} \frown d_{a_2} \frown \dots \frown d_{a_k}$ is the concatenation of the descriptions of the entity e_a (possibly from different chunks)⁴.

³Without loss of generality, we may assume that the numbering a_1, \dots, a_k is an increasing subsequence of the ordering $1, \dots, n$, i.e., that it is in accordance with the numbering of the chunks.

⁴The descriptions might be shortened by an LLM if the surpass some length threshold. This is important from the

We can describe the details of the procedure, by which the choice of the representatives is being done, using the language of matrix equations. This way, we get a more fine-grained characterization of the mathematical mechanics of the algorithm.

We embed these elements of the quotient-list of entities $\tilde{E} = \{\tilde{e}_1^1, \dots, \tilde{e}_{k'_1}^1, \tilde{e}_1^2, \dots, \tilde{e}_{k'_2}^2, \dots, \tilde{e}_1^n, \dots, \tilde{e}_{k'_n}^n\}$, into some l -dimensional vector space, using a specified embedder \mathcal{E} . For simplicity, let's use m as the number of elements of the list \tilde{E} . This way, we obtain an m -element list of l -dimensional vectors $\mathcal{E}(\tilde{E}) = (v_1, \dots, v_m)$, where for each $i \leq m$ we have $v_i = \mathcal{E}(e_i)$.

Additionally, we define an $m \times n$ -dimensional binary matrix $M_C = [t_{ij}]_{1 \leq i \leq m; 1 \leq j \leq n}$, where each row corresponds to an entity \tilde{e}_i , and each column corresponds to a chunk c_j , and $[t_{ij}] = 1$ iff the name n_i has been generated from the chunk c_j , that is: $t_{ij} = 1$ if n_i appears in c_j , and 0 otherwise. Obviously, there can be more than one 1s in i -th the verse of the matrix, if the name n_i occurs in more than one chunk.

Now, we perform the crucial step of the UnWeaver: given a query q , using a chosen similarity function σ , for each vector v_i , $i \leq m$, we compute the similarity $\sigma(v_i, \mathcal{E}(q))$ between the vector $\mathcal{E}(e_i)$, and the embedding of the query q . Now, given some k_0 , we compute the k_0 vectors v_i with the highest similarity scores $\sigma(v_i, \mathcal{E}(q))$, and we put $q_i := 1$ if v_i is among the top- k_0 ones, otherwise we put $q_i := 0$, and we refer to the binary vector consisting of entries q_i as M_q . Then we multiply each i -th row of M_C by the i -th entry of M_q ⁵, effectively filtering out the rows i of the matrix M_C which correspond to entities that are not semantically similar enough to the embedding of the query, that is we consider the intermediate filtering matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} q_1 t_{11} & q_1 t_{12} & \dots & q_1 t_{1n} \\ q_2 t_{21} & q_2 t_{22} & \dots & q_2 t_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ q_m t_{m1} & q_m t_{m2} & \dots & q_m t_{mn} \end{bmatrix},$$

and we delete the rows i for which $q_i = 0$, so that we obtain the modified matrix M'_C , which is a final filtered version of the binary matrix M_C with the

point of view of scalability.

⁵In other words, we pick the i -th row of M_q , which happens to be a vector of length 1, so without loss of generality we use the only scalar that is in this row.

same number of columns n , yet possibly a (much) smaller number of non-zero rows m' :

$$M'_C = \begin{bmatrix} q_{1'} t_{1'1} & q_{1'} t_{1'2} & \dots & q_{1'} t_{1'n} \\ q_{2'} t_{2'1} & q_{2'} t_{2'2} & \dots & q_{2'} t_{2'n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ q_{m'} t_{m'1} & q_{m'} t_{m'2} & \dots & q_{m'} t_{m'n} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_{1'1} & t_{1'2} & \dots & t_{1'n} \\ t_{2'1} & t_{2'2} & \dots & t_{2'n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ t_{m'1} & t_{m'2} & \dots & t_{m'n} \end{bmatrix},$$

where the last equality holds, since all the q_i 's are equal to 1. Finally, after depriving the non-sufficiently similar entities of their voting rights, we perform a multi-winner approval election, where the set of remaining (non-filtered) entities (i.e., the entities \tilde{e}_i , for which $q_i = 1$) are the set of voters, and the set of chunks $\{c_1, \dots, c_n\}$ is the set of candidates. Each row of the matrix M'_C corresponds to an approval ballot of the voter i , i.e., we postulate the the voter i approves of the chunk j iff $t_{i'j} = 1$. We compute the election, according to some chosen committee approval-based election rule⁶, assuming we need to choose a set of r chunks for some fixed $r < n$. The query response is then based only on the selected r chunks.

Benefits Observe that the solution is by far not ad-hoc. Already on the conceptual level, there are many benefits of entity-based representation:

- The conceptual model of entities is a ubiquitous element of human cognitive architecture, which supports the idea that this method of representing knowledge is efficient. Additionally, its naturality makes the functioning of the system more explainable and user-friendly.
- The same entity can occur in multiple chunks, which allows to integrate information, facilitating multi-hop question answering. These chunks can represent different spatiotemporal states, different contexts, or possibly different states-of-knowledge, allowing for modeling dynamics. Additionally, thanks to the discriminatory nature of UnWeaver, we easily get rid of superfluous or unrelated information contained in noisy coarse-grained chunks.
- Entities are naturally represented as belonging to a hierarchy of types (ontology). This allows for handling queries which require aggregation, i.e. exhaustive search over a selected domain of objects.

⁶This could be e.g., Approval, Proportional Approval, or Chamberlin-Courant.

Table 1: QA performance of RAG methods

dataset	Method	FC		LLM Tokens				Embedder Tokens	
		$\mu \uparrow$	σ^2	prompt		completion		index \downarrow	query
				index \downarrow	query \downarrow	index \downarrow	query \downarrow		
COVID-QA (1234 questions)	UnWeaver	0.3823	$1.32e^{-5}$	1466k	994k	4043k	230k	2224k	17k
	VectorRAG	0.3790	$6.02e^{-6}$	-	922k	-	359k	476k	17k
	RAPTOR	0.3643	$8.04e^{-6}$	770k	2649k	389k	305k	730k	17k
	GraphRAG	0.3092	$3.66e^{-6}$	25882k	7051k	14239k	282k	20455k	17k
eManual (522 questions)	UnWeaver	0.4811	$2.47e^{-5}$	98k	940k	198k	96k	105k	5.7k
	VectorRAG	0.4793	$2.16e^{-5}$	-	343k	-	83k	36k	5.7k
	RAPTOR	0.4466	$2.17e^{-5}$	57k	1177k	30k	115k	60k	5.7k
	GraphRAG	0.3424	$5.87e^{-6}$	1428k	3266k	687k	112k	1063k	5.7k
Tech-QA (596 questions)	UnWeaver	0.3135	$7.54e^{-6}$	3747k	2384k	4446k	158k	2411k	55k
	VectorRAG	0.3218	$7.86e^{-6}$	-	2354k	-	161k	3026k	55k
	RAPTOR	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	GraphRAG	0.2847	$4.19e^{-6}$	49270k	5944k	35704k	163k	54016k	55k

– The lack of limits of the number of entities extracted per chunk makes it possible to disentangle an arbitrary number of topics from a chunk therefore solving the inherent problem of mixing topics in naive vector representation of chunks.

3 Experimental Results

We evaluate the quality of RAG systems on downstream QA task with a selection of three datasets included in the distantly supervised RAGBench suite [6]. To identify the pitfalls and / or inefficiencies of graph-based RAG systems we compare our method against Microsoft’s GraphRAG[7] as well as RAPTOR[15]. GraphRAG was the system that sparked the domain of graph-based RAG systems, it performs a multi step indexing procedure that first extracts entities and relations and then builds a hierarchical communities using those entities. During retrieval it relies on heuristics to select communities, relations and entities in order to perform QA. Recently RAPTOR emerged and has been one of the dominant systems in graph-based RAGs in terms of its performance. It builds its index by recursively clustering summaries of chunks, it then makes use of that tree to perform QA. The last system we compare against as baseline is VectorRAG[14] that created the domain of RAG systems in the first place. All the methods are indexed and queried with

GPT-oss-120B LLM and embedded with **Qwen3-Embedding-4B**. To evaluate the quality of QA we employ calculation of Factual Correctness (F1) from RAGAS[5] which we average across all questions and calculate over 5 evaluation runs in order to get variance of the mean Factual Correctness for each method. In order to eliminate the effect of response formatting on FC score we fix the query prompt across all the methods to be the same. The results are listed in Table 1.

UnWeaver is the best system for eManual and COVID-QA, with being a close second place for Tech-QA⁷. The surprising fact is that VectorRAG is the main competitor across these datasets, with other Graph-based approaches lagging behind in terms of Factual Correctness. This can be partially explained by the architectural similarity of VectorRAG to the procedure for generating the original datasets.

The quality of answers should be also evaluated in tandem with Token Usage to estimate the cost and latency of indexing and querying the data. With the exception of eManual UnWeaver uses the least LLM tokens in the query phase, thereby providing the lowest query latency, effectively frontloading some of the effort into the indexing phase (as compared with

⁷On Tech-QA dataset, we were unable to produce results using RAPTOR despite numerous attempts. The problem was numerical instability in calculation of Gaussian Mixture Models that are the backbone of RAPTOR’s clustering procedure.

e.g. VectorRAG).

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A.1 Retrieval

Suppose we are given a query vector \mathbf{q} for which we need to prepare the context for response generation. That context must contain the retrieved relevant document chunks. The idea behind the UnWeaver-based retrieval exploits properties of the vector database \mathbf{V} to identify those chunks that are relevant to the query.

For the sake of illustration, let us take a look at simple models the VDB search. First, consider the orthogonal projection of \mathbf{q} onto the column-space of \mathbf{V} . That projection defines a vector in the column-space of \mathbf{V} that is closest to the query. It is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{V}^+\mathbf{q}, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{V}^+ is the Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse. Notice that to find a list of k embeddings of the extracted entity descriptions that are nearest to \mathbf{q} , it is in fact enough to calculate the Euclidean distance

$$\|\mathbf{V}(:, s) - \mathbf{q}\|_2^2 = \|\mathbf{V}(:, s) - (\hat{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{e})\|_2^2 = \|\mathbf{V}(:, s) - \hat{\mathbf{q}}\|_2^2 + \|\mathbf{e}\|_2^2, \quad (9)$$

which follows from the Pythagorean theorem for orthogonal vectors $\mathbf{V}(:, s) - \hat{\mathbf{q}}$ and \mathbf{e} (projection error). Then, the relevant database entries are index by

$$\hat{\sigma} = \text{Arg}_k \min(k)_{s=1, \dots, S} (\|\mathbf{V}(:, s) - \mathbf{q}\|_{s=1}^S). \quad (10)$$

We write $\min(k)$ (or $\max(k)$) to denote k best (min or max) elements of the list of numbers that follows.

The relevant context is now given by retrieval matrix

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{C}(:, \hat{\sigma})_{K \times k}, \quad (11)$$

a submatrix built from columns $\hat{\sigma}$ in of matrix \mathbf{C} .

Similarly, for the search based on cosine similarity, we have

$$\tilde{\sigma} = \text{Arg} \max(k)_{s=1, \dots, S} (\tilde{\mathbf{V}}(:, s)^T \tilde{\mathbf{q}})_{s=1}^S \quad \text{for} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{V}}(:, s) = \frac{\mathbf{V}(:, s)}{\|\mathbf{V}(:, s)\|} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\mathbf{q}} = \frac{\mathbf{q}}{\|\mathbf{q}\|}. \quad (12)$$

Here, the relevant context is also given by

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{C}(:, \tilde{\sigma})_{K \times k}. \quad (13)$$

The retrieval matrix is a binary matrix such that $r_{ij} = 1$ is chunk i contains description j that is one of top- k descriptions of ideas (entities of equivalence class) relevant to the query. Notice, that the same chunk may contain many such descriptions, an observation motivating our next step going beyond basic retrieval.

A.2 Alignment

The retrieval framework we have developed provides an interesting setting for retrieval alignment control. Notice that matrix \mathbf{C} , or its retrieval submatrix \mathbf{R} , can be interpreted as a routing matrix in the following well studied aggregate utility maximization problem:

$$\text{maximize} \quad \sum_{s=1}^S U_s(x_s) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{R}\mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{f} \quad \text{and (optionally)} \quad -\mathbf{I}_S \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{0}_{S \times 1}. \quad (14)$$

The related Lagrange function is then

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}) = \sum_{s=1}^S U_s(x_s) - \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T (\mathbf{R}\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{f}) + \boldsymbol{\mu}^T \mathbf{x}. \quad (15)$$

For a detailed study of the solutions to the problem, see e.g. [9, 10].

We want to find an optimal distribution $\bar{\mathbf{x}} = [x_1, \dots, x_S]^T$ of the strength of ideas (representatives of equivalence classes identified in \mathbf{T}) over the relevant document chunks (containing those ideas). However, the strength of ideas in each chunk cannot exceed an imposed upper bound \mathbf{f} that controls the distribution. That strength, defined by a given \mathbf{x} , is described by the product

$$\mathbf{R}\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_1^* \\ \text{---} \\ \vdots \\ \text{---} \\ \mathbf{r}_K^* \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}, \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{r}_k^* denotes row k of the matrix.

It follows from the KKT optimality conditions, that a solution $(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}})$ to the aligned retrieval problem satisfies the following system of inequalities:

$$U'_s(\bar{x}_s) \leq \sum_{i=1}^K r_{is} \bar{\lambda}_i, \text{ with equality for } \bar{x}_s > 0, \quad s = 1, \dots, S, \quad (17)$$

where $\bar{\lambda}_s$ denotes Lagrange multiplier for the mixing strength constraint $\mathbf{r}_k^* \mathbf{x} \leq f_k$ in chunk $k = 1, \dots, K$.

It is now clear that selecting the utility function U_s for each equivalence class (or extracted idea), together with the vector \mathbf{f} , allows for controlling the retrieval alignment. One theoretically elegant example includes

$$U_s(x_s) = \gamma_s(\mathbf{q}) \log(x_s) \text{ for } \gamma_s = \gamma_s(\mathbf{q}). \quad (18)$$

Here, weight γ_s could depend on the relevance of the available database entries in \mathbf{V} for given query \mathbf{q} vector. For example, we could set

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{q}. \quad (19)$$

Then, optimal distribution of chunks is given by the well recognized interpretable closed-form solution (reachable in a convergent iterative auction-like process, e.g., see [13]):

$$\bar{x}_s = \frac{\gamma_s}{\sum_{i=1}^K r_{is} \bar{\lambda}_i} = \frac{\mathbf{V}(:, s)^T \mathbf{q}}{\sum_{i=1}^K r_{is} \bar{\lambda}_i}. \quad (20)$$

Another straightforward and elegant approach we can propose, defines retrieval alignment as a constrained least squares problem:

$$\text{minimize } \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{V}\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{q}\|_2^2 \text{ s.t. } \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f}. \quad (21)$$

If \mathbf{f} belongs to the column space of \mathbf{V} , \mathbf{C} has independent rows, and $[\mathbf{A}^T \ \mathbf{C}^T]^T$ has independent columns, then the problem has a unique and interpretable closed form solution $(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}})$ meeting the KKT linear matrix equation $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{V} & \mathbf{C}^T \\ \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{x}} \\ \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{q} \\ \mathbf{f} \end{bmatrix}$. For the study of general and randomized solutions to that equation see e.g. [2, 11, 1].

Algorithm 1 Aligned Retrieval with UnWeaver

Require: Document \mathbf{T} , query q_{text} , embedding operator $\mathcal{E}: \mathcal{T}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^P$

Ensure: Context chunks

- 1: **Preprocessing:**
- 2: $[\mathbf{T}_1 | \dots | \mathbf{T}_K] \leftarrow \text{Tokenize}(\mathbf{T})$
- 3: Extract entities and descriptions: $\mathbf{A} \leftarrow [\mathbf{a}_{ij}]_{i=1, \dots, K}^{j=1, \dots, n}$, $\mathbf{W} \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times n}$
- 4: Identify equivalence classes: $\{\sigma(1), \dots, \sigma(S)\}$
- 5: **for** $s = 1$ to S **do** ▷ Representatives of equivalent classes
- 6: $\mathbf{P}_s \leftarrow \mathbf{I}_n(:, \sigma(s))$
- 7: $\mathbf{c}_s \leftarrow \text{sign}(\mathbf{W} \mathbf{P}_s \mathbf{1})$
- 8: $\mathbf{v}_s \leftarrow \mathcal{E}(\text{concat}(\mathbf{A} \mathbf{P}_s))$
- 9: **end for**
- 10: $\mathbf{C} \leftarrow [\mathbf{c}_1 | \dots | \mathbf{c}_S] \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times S}$
- 11: $\mathbf{V} \leftarrow [\mathbf{v}_1 | \dots | \mathbf{v}_S] \in \mathbb{R}^{P \times S}$
- 12: **Query Processing:**
- 13: $\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \mathcal{E}(q_{\text{text}})$
- 14: $\boldsymbol{\gamma} \leftarrow \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{q}$ ▷ Relevance scores for Retrieval Alignment
- 15: **Retrieval Alginment:**
- 16: **if** method = Utility-Based **then**
- 17: Find: $\arg \max_{\mathbf{x} \geq 0} \sum_{s=1}^S \gamma_s \log(x_s)$ s.t. $\mathbf{C} \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{f}$
- 18: Initialize: $\boldsymbol{\lambda} \leftarrow \mathbf{1}_K / K$
- 19: **for** $t = 1$ to t_{\max} **do**
- 20: $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow [\gamma_s / (\mathbf{C}(:, s)^T \boldsymbol{\lambda})]_{s=1}^S$ ▷ Primal update
- 21: $\boldsymbol{\rho} \leftarrow \mathbf{C} \mathbf{x}$
- 22: $\boldsymbol{\lambda} \leftarrow \text{UpdatePrices}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\rho}, \mathbf{f})$ ▷ Dual update
- 23: **if** $\|\boldsymbol{\rho} - \mathbf{f}\|_{\infty} < \epsilon$ **then break**
- 24: **end if**
- 25: **end for**
- 26: **else if** method = CLS **then**
- 27: Find: $\arg \min_{\mathbf{x}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{V} \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{q}\|_2^2$ s.t. $\mathbf{C} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f}$
- 28: Solve: $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{V} & \mathbf{C}^T \\ \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x} \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{q} \\ \mathbf{f} \end{bmatrix}$
- 29: **end if**
- 30: **Context Retrieval:**
- 31: $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \text{TopK}(\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{x}, k')$ ▷ Best equivalence classes
- 32: $\mathcal{I} \leftarrow \{i : \exists s \in \mathcal{S}, c_{is} = 1\}$ ▷ Relevant chunks
- 33: **return** $\{\mathbf{T}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}$

A.3 Numerical Example

Suppose we have already decomposed document \mathbf{T} into $K = 2$ chunks, and we extracted with an LLM entities forming $S = 3$ equivalent ideas (or equivalence classes). Let us assume that the distribution of those ideas in the chunks is

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (22)$$

and their concatenated descriptions are represented by the following matrix of embedding

$$\mathbf{V} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0.5 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.5 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

Given query $\mathbf{q} = [1 \ 1]^T$, we want to retrieve relevant chunks of text that are well aligned with our preferences for context generation. We set the budget of ideas in each chunk to $\mathbf{f} = [1 \ 1]^T$ and demand $L = 2$ to be kept in the retrieved context.

With this simple settings, we get

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (24)$$

and the retrieval alignment problem becomes:

$$\text{maximize } \sum_{s=1}^S \log(x_s) \text{ s.t. } \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f}. \quad (25)$$

It can be verified rather easily, that KKT conditions are satisfied for

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{3} \\ \frac{2}{3} \\ \frac{1}{3} \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{3}{2} \\ \frac{3}{2} \\ \frac{3}{2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

From that we conclude that the aligned retrieval generates context consisting of the relevant chunks

$$\bar{\sigma} = \{1, 2\}. \quad (27)$$

B Prompts

This is the query prompt that was used across all methods.

Role: System

Content:

You are a question answering system.
Please make sure that the answer is correct and complete.
At the same time avoid redundancy and irrelevant information.
Please try to answer the question in Single Sentence.

Do so based on the following context:

{context}

Role: User

Content:

{question}